

CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR CIGESMED: INVOLVING DIVERS IN MARINE BIOLOGICAL MONITORING

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Mediterranean coralline reefs, known as “coralligenous”, are bioherms built by calcifying rhodophytes on hard substrates in dim-light conditions. They are hotspots of biodiversity, harbouring rich assemblages and valuable biological resources. The assemblages they host are popular among SCUBA divers due to their complex structure, conspicuous biological wealth and high aesthetic value. Nevertheless, data on their distribution, structure and conservation status is still scarce for several Mediterranean areas (e.g. southern and eastern sectors). These habitats are also vulnerable to multiple anthropic pressures, alongside with sea surface warming and biological invasions.

Over the last decade, inventorying and monitoring of marine biodiversity has significantly benefited from the active engagement of volunteers. Although several Citizen Science projects concern tropical reef ecosystems, none of the existing initiatives has yet specifically focused on their Mediterranean equivalents. Citizen Science for CIGESMED is a European project aiming to engage enthusiast divers in the study and monitoring of Mediterranean coralligenous assemblages through the gathering of some simplified information. A specific protocol for underwater observation was developed along with data-recording dive slates, to acquire information about: (a) basic topographic and abiotic features for the preliminary description of each site and the creation of data series for sites receiving multiple visits, (b) presence and relative abundance of typical conspicuous species, as well as (c) existence of pressures and imminent threats, for the characterization and assessment of coralligenous assemblages.

The testing of the protocol and the associated guidance material was achieved through the involvement of volunteer divers in preliminary field trials at different areas of the Mediterranean. In order to test the reliability of the protocol and identify possible correction factors for the obtained datasets, the validity of the answers provided by divers was assessed in comparison to those provided by scientists. The results showed that for few species (e.g. small-sized ones with a patchy/sparse distribution in the study site) the abundance was underestimated. Some pressures also appeared difficult to identify and (semi-) quantify. Future efforts will aim to maximize the engagement of the enthusiast participants, train the less competent ones, and enhance the communication between citizen scientists and professional researchers.